

How to reference: Obot, E. E. and Obot, P. E. (2019). Social Media and News Credibility: A Question of Integrity. *Akwapoly Journal of Mass communication*, 1(2)78-89

Social Media and News Credibility: A Question of Integrity

By

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ABSTRACT

The advent of social media has added colour to news reporting across the globe. The speed with which information gets to millions of people through Facebook or Twitter speaks of the huge advantage of these platforms in spreading information rapidly across social systems while promoting citizen journalism where virtually everyone could get to collect, analyse and disseminate news through the internet. With this access to the internet, almost everyone has become a journalist since social media remains an open space where people can post and share messages whether such messages are true or false. Moreover, with the large volume of content produced and shared online, it is near impossible for most of these contents to be scrutinised so as to protect people from being misinformed. However, where integrity and news credibility is not considered by the 'journalist' reporting through social media, an unhealthy and misleading agenda could be set for public discussions thus, encouraging a build-up of negative emotions such as hatred or disputes among people. The focus of this paper therefore, is to re-emphasise the need for integrity in news reporting, while also x-raying the dangers of unhealthy news reporting to our society.

Keywords: Social Media, Credibility, News, Social Responsibility and Integrity

Introduction

The speed with which information gets across to millions of people through social media is quite interesting. According to Saaris (2015), one of the most important advantages of social media is certainly the speed and efficiency with which it allows communication between people. On a daily basis, messages on issues ranging from health, governance, social life, fashion to environmental are created, posted and shared through these platforms for public consumption. The interesting aspect of using these platforms to spread information is the speed with which messages could be viewed, read and shared by millions of people simultaneously. Highlighting some advantages of social media, Saaris (2015) observes that it has been used to increase awareness of social and political issues as well as organise demonstrations. According to the researcher, the ability of users to conveniently stay in touch with friends and family who live far away, connect with like-minded people, and expand business contacts tells of the huge advantages of these platforms. Similarly, Illahi, as cited by Farid (2016), asserts that social media has given new impetus to citizen journalism where people now have the power to share any kind of information by a single click. Although this power is often misused by rumour mongers that have found a new tool to create panic in the society.

Through social media, almost everyone has become a 'journalist'. Kombol, Edache and Abutu (2016) is of the opinion that in some way, the benefits of citizen journalism is that ordinary citizens get to share information online or with a conventional media personnel that possibly was not present at the place of incidence. For this reason among others, social media users are not just content observers or critics but also content producers. This is because the internet remains an open space with great ease of access and a minimum level of control.

Meaning that almost anyone with an internet complaint device has an opportunity to be heard or subscribe to any social media platform. According to Kombol *et.al* (2016)), the advent and proliferation of the internet and its corresponding media have created new markets and forms of journalism where journalists work as online journalists, content managers or editors for websites, blogs or even social media pages”.

Since the “social media depend on mobile and web-based technologies to create highly interactive platforms through which individuals and communities share, co-create, discuss, and modify user-generated content” (Li and Suh 2015, p. 314), virtually anyone with access to the internet could become a member of any social media. Hence, the freedom to post or share messages at will, thereby spurring citizen journalism. According to Kombol *et.al* (2016), the internet as helpful as it has been to journalists and the journalism profession has opened a new ground that is in turn proving to be a threat to professionalism. In other words,

the internet signals the radical shift in the ‘who’ is in control of information; experiences and resources whereby everybody in the society is now a reporter. These modifications have altered news reading habits between readers and content creators since the internet has reduced the time needed for the processing and delivery of news stories (Kombol *et.al* 2016).

This important consideration in journalism practice is often carried out in order to ensure accuracy and objectivity in news/information report so as to ensure that people are not being misled. This is because there are people who are immediately persuaded by messages whether such messages are true or false and would immediately re-broadcast them by clicking on the share buttons without verifying the credibility of such news or the source.

Moreover, there are people who may just be waiting to tag a lot of family and friends to news stories so as to get them informed about happenings as quick as possible. Information on social media platforms suffers from a lack of professional gatekeepers to monitor content and

it is not unusual to find that unverified or falsified information continues to flood on social media (Li and Suh, 2015). Hence, the need to re-emphasise credibility in reporting news through social media is of essence.

Social Media as a News Source

For the purpose of this study, a survey was conducted on the usage of social media among some internet users. Findings from the focus group survey of 20 internet users revealed that social media remains a potential primary source of news among people (see tables 1,2, 3 and 4).

Table 1: Do you access news through social media?

Response	Frequency	Percentage
Yes	20	100%
No	-	
Maybe	-	
Total	20	100%

Source: Field Survey, 2019

Table 2: If yes, how often do you access news through social media?

Response	Frequency	Percentage
Daily	17	85%
Weekly	3	15%
Monthly	-	-
Yearly	-	-
Total	20	100%

Source: Field Survey, 2019

Table 3: Which of the following Social Media do you get most of your news from?

Response	Frequency	Percentage
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Facebook	15	75%
Twitter	3	15%
Whatsapp	-	-
Instagram	-	-
YouTube	2	10%
Total	20	100%

Source: *Field Survey, 2019*

Table 4: How often have you accessed news through social media but later discovered that it was not true or misleading?

Response	Frequency	Percentage
Very Often	1	5%
Often	18	90%
Not at all	1	5%
Total	20	100%

Source: *Field Survey, 2019*

Similar studies have shown that over the years, social media platforms have served as great sources of news. A study conducted in 2012 from Pew Research Centre showed that over 48% of the respondents claimed to have accessed news through social media. In a survey on News Use across Social Media Platforms, Gottfried and Shearer (2016), reveal that the majority of the sampled respondents' got their news from social media. As shown in the study, two-thirds of Facebook users (66%) got news from Facebook while nearly six-in-ten Twitter users (59%) got news on Twitter and seven-in-ten Reddit users got news on Reddit.

According to Wakefield (2016), social media has overtaken television as young people's main source of news. Collins (2016) agrees that the majority of the younger audience now gets their primary news through social media. With so many people having access to smart mobile

devices and the internet, visiting a traditional newspaper stand to purchase news may be considered a waste of time or energy since we are living in the age of information explosion where the internet brings people closer to much information on a daily basis.

In a study conducted by Oyero (2016) on the use and believability of social networks news among Nigerian youths, the researcher reveals that (95.4%) of the respondents said they used social media as sources of news. On preference for getting news/information from various media, (70.3%) said they preferred the social media while (65%) of the respondents claimed their primary source of news was the social media with Facebook ranking the highest.

Lawrence (2012) in a similar study further reveals that out of 400 people surveyed, more than 1 in 4 persons regularly got news from social media and over half had found out about breaking stories through social media before it appeared on official news channels. As noted by the researcher, Facebook users (70%) got most of their news from friends and families while (13%) got news from organisations and journalists. On Twitter, (36%) got news links from friends and family as opposed to the (27%) who got it from traditional news organisations and journalists.

These studies all point to the fact that social media has come to stay as primary sources of news and information for many people. With the internet and especially smart mobile devices, access to news and information dissemination among people has become very easy. With many social media platforms emerging, the exchange and interspersing of knowledge and ideas among people will continue to proliferate.

Social media and News Credibility

Opinions differ as to whether social media could serve as credible channels of news dissemination. Wathen and Burkell, cited by Li and Suh (2015), posit that we encounter a great deal of information in our daily life and one of the criteria we use to filter information is its credibility or believability. Although these scholars did not explain further how credibility and believability helps in the filtering of information we receive, it is important to point out that the knowledge and faith people have in a news source and the channel for disseminating the news plays a huge role on how messages are received, filtered or perceived to be credible or not.

It is no longer a new thing that news could be found or accessed through the social media but the question would be to ask; to what extent could this news be considered credible or not? This is due to the fact that the internet remains an open space with little or no control and these media channels have also been greatly abused by rumour mongers to spread falsified information with intent to cause fear and panic among members of the society. As shown in table 4 of this paper, 90% of the respondents claimed to have been often disappointed with news got from the social media. According to the respondents, they frequently get to find out that the news they read on social media was never true. This result reveals that with ease of access to social media platforms, people with negative motives could send across fabricated information to the public just for their pleasure or any other reasons as it pleases. However, Ibold (2012) strikes a balance by arguing that the social media could be used to get us closer to the truth even though they could also be used to distort the truth. They could be used to enlighten the public and they could also be used to stupefy the public.

Journalism is a profession that is guided by some ethics which one of them is to ensure accuracy and objectivity in news reporting. These functions are best carried out during the processing and examining of news content before delivery for public consumption by trained professionals. The fact that the social media suffers from a lack of professional gatekeepers as required of the journalism profession is a serious concern to the credibility of the news that comes through these platforms. Almost everyone has become a 'journalist' without undergoing the required training as required of the profession thereby causing a raise of eyebrows as to what comes out from these platforms. This is not to say that all the news/information obtained from the social media are less credible but these media channels have been greatly used to amplify issues beyond their originality by 'citizen journalists'.

Nevertheless, on whether news found on social media are credible or not, is a function of the social media user. In other words, perceived credibility of a news story on the social media may be viewed based on the users' satisfaction of such news, upon confirmation with other news sources in order to ensure the validity and authenticity of the news. According to Fogg and Tseng as cited by Westerman, Spence and Heide (2014, p. 173), "It is important to consider that credibility is a perception, and thus is not a quality inherent within a channel or source itself". Therefore, many things can impact the perceived credibility of online materials (Metzger, Flanagan, Eyal, Lemus, and McCann as cited by Westerman *et.al* (2014, p. 173).

Just as it is popularly said that money does not know good or evil but it is the hand that holds the money that knows what to use it for; whether good or evil. The same could be said about social media. These platforms are only channels to spread information or keep people in contact with each other. It is only humans with their hands and minds that can determine what information is created, posted or shared through social media. It is therefore left for the

content creator to judge if the message being released across social systems would be misleading or not, considering the fact that no two persons may understand or interpret a message the same way. However, Abbasi and Liu (2012, p. 3) aver that “in traditional media as well as social media, the credibility of the source has a great effect on the process of acquiring the content and changing audience attitudes and beliefs.”

Theoretical Framework

The discussion of this paper is steered using the Uses and Gratifications theory originated from the work of Katz, Blummer and Gurevitchm in 1974 and the Social Responsibility Theory which finds its origin from Hutchins 1947 Commission on the Freedom of the press.

The central argument of the Uses and Gratifications Theory is on what people do with the media rather than what the media do to people. This theory explains that people choose or use the media based on how much their needs are met by such media. In other words, the choice of media is based on the gratification the user gets from the media. According to Ndolo (2005), there is however no uniformity in the way individuals use the media, how long they use and for what reasons. Hence, the differences in the way people react to media messages.

The relevance of the theory to this work is that on a daily basis people are blogging, facebooking or tweeting with their smart mobile devices. The gratifications that people get in using social media to either share information or stay in close contact with loved one is quite enormous. According to Agbo (2016, p. 70), “social media have now become almost an inseparable part of human life in places where they exist.” On Facebook for example, millions of people are tagged to view stories, comment or share with others.

On the other hand, though there is a great ease of access to the social media where users can either build or set up agenda for public discussions, the social responsibility role of the media to society should not be forgotten. According to Kenechukwu (2014, p. 36) “through the media, we learn almost everything we know about the world beyond our environments”. Thus, the media play a huge role in shaping and moulding of public opinion on so many issues in society. Through social media, people are at ease to either set a healthy or an unhealthy agenda for public discussions. Hence, the need to consider public interest as a priority.

According to *Pachamama Alliance* (n. d), the theory of social responsibility is built on a system of ethics in which decisions and actions must be ethically validated. Meaning that, the benefit of an action to the society must be first considered by a person before such action is taken. In this way, there must be a balance between economic growth, the society’s welfare and the environment. According to this theory, no matter the ease of access to various social media platforms where people have the liberty to post or share any information online, the society’s interest should be at the forefront to every content creator. Every entity, be it an organisation or individual, has an obligation to act for the benefit of society at large (Wikipedia). According to McQuail as cited in Upadhyay and Dang (2014, p. 125),

the main public interest criteria that the media need to consider include freedom of publication, plurality in media ownership, diversity in information, culture and opinion, support for the democratic political system, support for public order and security of the state, universal reach, quality of information and culture disseminated to the public, respect for human rights and avoiding harm to individuals and society.

Dangers of Unhealthy News Reporting through the Social Media

The primary functions of the mass media are to inform, educate and entertain. For these reasons, millions of people depend on the media for information about things happening around them. According to Happer and Philo (2013, p. 1), “the media play a central role in informing the public about what happens in the world, particularly in those areas in which audiences do not possess direct knowledge or experience”. As noted by Udomisor and Kenneth (2013, p. 1), “a situation where news selection and presentation is based on material gratifications instead of public goals and interest, stands against the ethics of the profession and is anti-public unity and development”.

The fact that the internet, especially through social media, has given rise to citizen journalism does not mean that the code of ethics which guides the profession of journalism should be ignored by the ‘supposed journalists’. The media play a fundamental role in notifying the public about events in the society thus, shaping and moulding public opinion on several issues. If public interest is not seen or placed as a priority in designing, posting and sharing news/information through social media, unhealthy information could be released into the society.

Considering the number of people who access the social media on a daily basis, there are high possibilities of people to be negatively influenced by misleading information. In other words, as this fabricated information gets to circulate across social systems, there is likelihood that people may begin to debate or discuss about what they saw or read on social media. The result of these debates may however, lead to a build-up of negative emotions such as hatred or quarrels among the people, thereby causing harm to society.

When people are misguided for selfish purposes or whatever, a grave damage is being done to the society. This is because; unhealthy information could be perilous to the growth of a nation. It could lead to negative arguments which may even result in clashes, hostility and at extreme cases, shedding of blood. Li and Suh (2015, p. 325) point out that “while the growing popularity of the use of social media platforms, especially Facebook and its potentials to propagate misinformation, the ability to judge credible information is becoming more important.” According to the researchers, social media users need to pay attention to information credibility because online rumour may cause serious harm to individuals and society.

Conclusion/Recommendations

It is important to note that people stand a chance of being influenced by whatever information gets across to them through social media. McCombs (2011) points out that the pictures in people’s minds about the outside world are significantly influenced by the mass media and the effects have significant implications beyond the pictures created in people’s heads. Therefore, as observed by McQuail (2000, p. 150), “the media have an obligation to the wider society and media ownership is a public trust”. In other words, without the people there would be no media. For this reason, the news media should be truthful, precise, fair and unbiased, following agreed codes of ethics and professional conduct.

This paper recommends that people need to be careful about what information they get from social media, bearing in mind that the internet remains an open space with a minimum level of control. Thus, people should put on their scrutinising and filtering antennas in order to ascertain the trustworthiness of news accessed through social media since nearly everyone can post and share information through these platforms. This is because social media could

be a reliable source of news only if the information obtained is scrutinised or analysed with other sources in order to verify the authenticity and accuracy of such news/information.

Though social media could be seen as sources of news, the issue of news credibility on these platforms is at the discretion of both the content creators and the receivers of these messages to judge. Credibility remains a function of perception; hence, it is the job of the 'journalist' to verify the content that is being shared for the sake of the public waiting to consume such information. Information that is not aimed at revealing the truth but only to mislead the public, causing strife and disaffections among members of the public should be avoided by social media users. Every 'citizen' should have it in mind that they have a fundamental obligation to the society, which is to serve the interest of the public over personal interest.

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